

Ion Exchange Equilibrium Studies with Some Strong Acid-weak Base Salts

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Ion exchange equilibria of two strong acid-weak base salts with styrene-divinylbenzene copolymer based sulphononic acid cation exchange resins of different relative degree of crosslinking have been studied.

Earlier¹, ion exchange equilibrium studies of some weak acid-strong base salts with styrene divinylbenzene copolymer based sulphononic acid cation exchange resins have been reported. This study summarises results of the work with two strong acid-weak base salts; this is of interest, as such studies are not available.

EXPERIMENTAL

The resins were from the samples used in the earlier work^{1,2} and the chemicals were of A. R. grade. Aniline hydrochloride was prepared by passing gaseous hydrochloric acid in a solution of distilled aniline in ether. The precipitated aniline hydrochloride was filtered, washed with ether and vacuum-dried at room temperature in a desiccator. The solution was prepared using freshly prepared salt by dissolving a known weight in distilled water and was rechecked by titration (bromination method)³. Pyridine hydrochloride solution was prepared by mixing solutions containing equivalent amounts of pyridine and

FIG. 1. Plot of the selectivity coefficient for pyridinium-hydrogen exchange against X_2 for constant values of X_1 .

1. D. J. Patel, R. A. Bhatt and S. L. Bafna, *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 43, 648.
2. S. S. Kanhere, D. J. Patel, R. S. Shah, R. A. Bhatt and S. L. Bafna, *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.*; 1965, 42, 589. Errata (November 1965).

hydrochloric acid and then suitably diluting with distilled water. In anilinium-hydrogen exchange studies, estimation was done by bromination method³. In pyridinium-hydrogen exchange studies, estimation was done by ultraviolet absorption at 256 m μ with Beckman model DU spectrophotometer using 10 mm quartz cells in presence of hydrochloric acid (10^{-2} N). The presence of hydrochloric acid above 10^{-2} N has no measurable effect on ultraviolet absorption at 256 m μ . The procedure for ion exchange equilibrium studies and the symbols used are as given earlier^{1,2}.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figures 1 and 2 indicate that the selectivity coefficient first increases and then decreases in anilinium-hydrogen exchange and continuously decreases in pyridinium-hydrogen exchange with increase in $\bar{X}_M$. This behaviour may be contrasted with that for the strong acid-strong base salts and weak acid-strong base salts^{1,2}. For a resin of particular X, this effect is to be attributed to the changes in the first two terms of equation (1) in earlier paper¹. Small contribution may also be attributed to some volume change in the resin particle as $\bar{X}_M$ increases. Another contributory reason may be that the resins, particularly of higher X, may be to some extent micro-heterogeneous⁴.

FIG. 2. Variation of selectivity coefficient for pyridinium-hydrogen exchange with $\bar{X}_M$ in chloride solution for resins of different X.

- | | |
|--------|-------------------|
| 1. X=1 | 4. X=12 |
| 2. X=4 | 5. X=16 |
| 3. X=8 | 6. X=Resin IR-200 |

From figures 1 and 2 the values of the selectivity coefficients were obtained for definite values of $\bar{X}_M$ for resins of different X, for anilinium-hydrogen exchange and pyridinium-hydrogen exchange. In figures 3 and 4 the selectivity coefficients thus obtained are plotted for constant values of $\bar{X}_M$, against X and the plots are quite characteristic. This behaviour is to be attributed to the changes in the second and third terms of equation (1)².

3. "Organic Analysis". Interscience publishers, Inc. New York. Vol. 3, p 185 (1956).

4. J. A. Kitchener; "Ion-exchange resins", Methuen 1957.

For resin IR-200 the values for the selectivity coefficients of anilinium-hydrogen exchange and pyridinium-hydrogen exchange were obtained from figures 1 and 2 at

FIG. 3. Plot of the selectivity coefficient for anilinium-hydrogen exchange against X for constant values of $\bar{X}_M$.

FIG. 4. Variation of selectivity coefficient for anilinium-hydrogen exchange with $\bar{X}_M$, in chloride solution for resins of different X .

- | | |
|----------|-----------------|
| 1. $X=1$ | 5. $X=12$ |
| 2. $X=2$ | 6. $X=16$ |
| 3. $X=4$ | 7. $X=20$ |
| 4. $X=8$ | 8. Resin IR-200 |

definite values of $\bar{X}_M$ and then from figures 3 and 4 the values of X were read out. The obtained values for X are given in Table I and indicate that the values for X vary

TABLE I

Values of X for resin IR-200 obtained from figures 3 and 4.

$\bar{X}_M$	Anilinium-hydrogen exchange	Pyridinium-hydrogen exchange
	$X=$	$X=$
0.30	9.2	10.3
0.40	7.0	4.5
0.50	4.2	1.0
0.60	2.2	—
0.70	0.8	—

significantly. This supports the conclusion that the resin IR-200 is structurally different from other resins used, though it is also a styrene-divinylbenzene copolymer based sulphonic acid resin².